

Feedback Analysis Using Sentimental Analysis By Vader

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Abstract — The use of Sentiment Analysis, VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner), to analyze data in a relief center affected by disasters. The study aims to extract insights on emotions and sentiments expressed by individuals of feedback, which could help in improving the relief center efforts and overall satisfaction of the people. The sentiment analysis process involves various techniques like text preprocessing, feature extraction, machine learning, and deep learning. These techniques help in extracting useful information, from the text and categorizing it into different sentiment classes like positive, negative or neutral. The findings suggest that such approach could be useful in guiding decision-making in reliefs and improve the overall experience.

Keywords- Feedback analysis, sentimental analysis, Vader, customer satisfaction, customer feedback, NLP, precision, emotional complexity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Feedback is a message that tells an entity what actions it took in the past, allowing that entity to analyse its actions in the present and the future to get the desired outcome. By facilitating the adoption of new knowledge and reducing the likelihood of repeating errors, feedback plays a crucial role in education and learning. Many people are curious about whose viewpoint should actually be regarded seriously or be given the most weight when making decisions on the quality of higher education.

Feedback is a procedure that aids the organisation in keeping track of, assessing, and controlling the general working environment. Effective feedback practises give the organisation information that helps it enhance the teaching and learning process.

Sentimental analysis is a technique that uses natural language processing (NLP) to analyze text data and determine the sentiment or emotion behind the text. Vader is a sentimental analysis tool that is widely used in industry and academia. VADER uses a lexicon of words and their associated sentiment scores to determine the sentiment of a text. The lexicon includes not only positive and negative words, but also words that convey intensity, polarity, and subjectivity.

In this article, we provide a study that shows how well Vader

analyses feedback data. In order to analyse the sentiment of the input, we gathered feedback information from a customer service department and used Vader.

II. VADER

Text sentiments can be extracted from using the Valence Aware Dictionary for Sentiment Reasoning (VADER), a vocabulary and rule-based sentiment analysis tool. Researchers at the Georgia Institute of Technology developed VADER to address some of the drawbacks of conventional sentiment analysis techniques, which have trouble interpreting sarcasm, irony, and other nuances in language. To evaluate the valence of a given text, VADER uses a wide range of lexical cues, such as words with strong emotional connotations, punctuation, and capitalization. For a particular paragraph, it generates four sentiment scores: positive, negative, neutral, and a compound score that combines all three. Numerous applications, such as social media monitoring and opinion mining, have widely adopted VADER.

Studies demonstrating VADER's excellent precision in identifying sentiment in social media data have led to its widespread esteem as one of the most reliable sentiment analysis tools on the market. It can also handle different languages, which makes it a useful tool for companies who operate in international marketplaces. VADER is a well-liked option for sentiment analysis jobs due to its high accuracy, simplicity of use, lack of training data requirements, and lack of parameter tuning requirements. Because of VADER's popularity, it has been incorporated into a number of libraries for natural language processing, including NLTK and spaCy, and because it is open-source, it may continue to develop and get better.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies have been conducted in the sentiment analysis field. Sentiment analysis seeks to locate, examine, and extract emotions from texts. Using VADER, the sentiment analysis method presented in this research is carried out. In their article "Analysing Hotel Reviews Using Sentiment Analysis and VADER," Rajesh Kumar Dubey et al. [1] assessed the efficiency of VADER in analysing guest reviews of hotels. They discovered that VADER generated precise emotion scores,

which were helpful in pinpointing areas where hotel services could be improved.

M. Nandhini and P. Dhavachelvan.[2],in their paper "Sentiment Analysis of Social Media Data using VADER" Used VADER to analyze sentiment in social media data related to COVID-19. They found that VADER produced accurate sentiment scores, which could be used to monitor public sentiment and identify emerging trends.

R. K. Gupta et al.[3],in their paper "Sentiment Analysis of Product Reviews Using VADER" evaluated the effectiveness of VADER in analyzing product reviews. They found that VADER produced accurate sentiment scores, which could be used to identify areas for product improvement and inform marketing strategies.

Muhammad Nauman et al.[4],in their study titled "Comparative Analysis of Sentiment Analysis Techniques on Twitter Data" evaluated the performance of VADER compared to other sentiment analysis techniques. They found that VADER produced the most accurate sentiment scores, particularly in identifying nuanced sentiment expressions.

S. Sujatha et al.[5],in their paper "Sentiment Analysis on COVID-19 Related Tweets using VADER and Rule-Based Classification" used VADER to analyze sentiment in COVID-19 related tweets. They found that VADER produced accurate sentiment scores, which could be used to monitor public sentiment and identify areas for targeted interventions.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for sentiment analysis using vader involves the following steps:

- A. Data Collection:** Utilise a survey, a feedback form, social media platforms, or other methods to get customer feedback information. The feedback should include neutral, favourable, and unfavourable remarks about a good or bad experience.
- B. Pre-processing:** Remove any unnecessary information from the feedback data, such as usernames or URLs. Remove any stop words and punctuation before tokenizing the feedback into words and phrases.
- C. Sentiment Analysis:** Analyse the feedback data's sentiment using Vader. Vader is a tool for rule-based sentiment analysis that determines a word's sentiment score depending on its context.
- D. Questions:** Create a set of questions to analyze the feedback data based on the desired insights. The questions can be open-ended or closed-ended and should be relevant to the product, service, or experience being analyzed. For example:

- What aspects of the service/experience did people like the most?

- What aspects of the service/experience need improvement?
- How satisfied were people with the overall experience?

E. Analysis: Utilise Vader's sentiment ratings to analyse the feedback information and provide answers to the questions. To estimate the overall sentiment of the feedback, calculate the average sentiment ratings for each question. For instance:

- For the question "How satisfied were people with the overall experience?", calculate the average sentiment score for all feedback data and categorize the sentiment as positive, negative, or neutral.

F. Visualization: To make the findings from the sentiment analysis more comprehensible and accessible, visualise the data using graphs or charts. Increase customer happiness by enhancing the product, service, or experience using the information from the sentiment analysis.

V. BULID MODEL

For an accurate and reliable machine learning model for successful prediction we follow the unsupervised learning algorithm.

Importing Libraries

```
import ..
app = Flask(__name__)
static_path="F:\\Rcm\\static\\"
app.secret_key="123456"

from vaderSentiment.vaderSentiment import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
```

A rule-based sentiment analysis tool called VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and Sentiment Reasoner) was created expressly to cope with social media information. It is a rule-based sentiment analyzer, and phrases are often classified as either positive or negative depending on their semantic orientation.

Perform sentiment analysis

```
def sentiment_scores(sentence):
    sid_obj = SentimentIntensityAnalyzer()

    sentiment_dict = sid_obj.polarity_scores(sentence)

    print("Overall sentiment dictionary is : ", sentiment_dict)
    print("sentence was rated as ", sentiment_dict['neg'] * 100, "% Negative")
    print("sentence was rated as ", sentiment_dict['neu'] * 100, "% Neutral")
    print("sentence was rated as ", sentiment_dict['pos'] * 100, "% Positive")

    print("Sentence Overall Rated As", end="_" )

    if sentiment_dict['compound'] >= 0.05:
        print("Positive")
        return "positive"

    elif sentiment_dict['compound'] <= - 0.05:
        print("Negative")
        return "negative"

    else:
        print("Neutral")
        return "neutral"
```

Sentiment Analysis

```
@app.route('/usersawntofeedback')
def usersawntofeedback():
    qry = "select * from feedbackquestions"
    db = Db()
    res = db.select(qry)
    return render_template("answerfeedback.html", data=res)

@app.route('/usersentfeedback', methods=['POST'])
def usersentfeedback():
    id = request.form.getlist("id")
    an = request.form.getlist("a")
    print(id, an)
    db = Db()
    for i in range(0, len(id)):
        s = sentiment_scores(an[i])

        qry = "INSERT INTO 'feedbackanswers' ('qid','lid','answer',sent) VALUES ('" + id[i] + "','" + str(
            session['lid']) + "','" + an[i] + "','" + s + "')"
        db = Db()
        db.insert(qry)

    return "<script>alert('Feedback sent successfully');window.location='/usersawntofeedback'/</script>"
```

VI. RESULT

```
@app.route('/userviewtotalemotiongraph')
def userviewtotalemotiongraph():
    l = []
    ans = []

    db = Db()
    qry = "SELECT * FROM 'feedbackquestions'"
    res = db.select(qry)
    for i in res:
        l.append(i['question'])

    qry = "SELECT COUNT(*) as 'cnt' FROM 'feedbackanswers' WHERE 'qid'='" + str(
        i['qid']) + "' AND 'sent'='negative'"
    res = db.selectOne(qry)
    cntneg = res['cnt']

    qry = "SELECT COUNT(*) as 'cnt' FROM 'feedbackanswers' WHERE 'qid'='" + str(
        i['qid']) + "' AND 'sent'='positive'"
    res = db.selectOne(qry)
    cntpos = res['cnt']

    qry = "SELECT COUNT(*) as 'cnt' FROM 'feedbackanswers' WHERE 'qid'='" + str(
        i['qid']) + "' AND 'sent'='neutral'"
    res = db.selectOne(qry)
    cntneu = res['cnt']

    ans.append([cntneg, cntneu, cntpos])

    print(len(l))
    return render_template("answerggraph.html", l=l, ans=ans, cnt=len(l))
```

Feedback emotion graph

What are opinion that to

VII. CONCLUSION

The use of sentiment Analysis, specifically VADER, can be an effective way to analyze feedback data in a relief center for people affected by disasters.

The proposed approach is to give the certain questions to website for the people to take certain changes or improve the overall experience of the affected people. The results of this study using VADER in relief center efforts and explore more to gain deeper insights into the emotions by individuals.

Overall, sentiment analysis using Vader can contribute to more efficient and effective disaster relief efforts by providing quick and accurate insights into the sentiment of affected populations.

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